

Bachelorthesis

TRANSFORMING NORMAL SPEECH INTO RAISED-VOCAL-
EFFORT SPEECH

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Declaration

I hereby declare that I have completed this thesis alone and without any unauthorised or external help. I further declare that all the sources, references, literature and any other associated resources have been correctly and appropriately cited and referenced. The confidentiality of the project provider (industry partner) as well as the intellectual property rights of the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts have been fully and entirely respected in the completion of this thesis.

Place / Date, Signature Dottikon/05.01.2026,

Expression of thanks and gratitude

I want to thank Dr Ludovic Amruthalingam and Laurent Simon for the support, inputs, and critical feedback throughout the project.

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Dottikon, December 2025

Lenny Simoni

I Abstract

In the hearing aid industry, it is important to be able to conduct experiments in real-life scenarios. In this context, a case of Lombard speech is an important and realistic scenario. However, recording is time-consuming and costly. In order to be able to carry out these experiments, it is essential to have sufficient data. Accordingly, there is interest in generating synthetic data via speaking style conversion. This thesis aims to establish a speaking style conversion system, evaluate it using objective metrics, and finally conduct a subjective evaluation using a listening test. Since there is currently little literature on speaking style conversion with respect to Lombard speech, this thesis also aims to provide a summary of the most important studies.

The task was initially defined during the **initiation phase**. A risk analysis was then carried out. The analysis includes a risk map and a list of possible risks associated with the project.

During the **concept phase**, the project's timetable was created. This defined the work packages and milestones and provided a rough estimate of the process. In addition, checkpoints were established to monitor the project's progress. The initial idea was recorded to develop the concept entirely during the implementation phase.

The **implementation phase** involved completing the defined goals. This phase included testing different approaches outlined in the studies, creating a baseline transformation and presenting the ElevenLabs solution. ElevenLabs makes it possible to clone a voice using audio files and then perform text-to-speech synthesis. This approach offers a workaround in the form of speech-to-text-to-speech synthesis. In addition, a subjective evaluation was conducted using the samples generated via the Soundsurvey platform. The analysis shows that ElevenLabs leads to a robust target with significant results.

Ultimately, a final meeting was held during the **deployment phase** to discuss the results and hand over the project. This meeting has been held between the author, the advisor, and the client.

Most of the defined goals were achieved during the course of the project. The literature review was successfully conducted to build a foundation of knowledge on the topic and identify the most important studies. Objective evaluation metrics commonly used in signal processing were also selected to measure the quality of the results. In addition, a solution was tested and evaluated. Finally, a subjective listening test was conducted in cooperation with Sonova.

Thus, 4 out of 5 goals are consistent with the established goals.

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1 Problem, Question and Vision

The following chapter discusses the initial situation and the problem definition. It also describes the tasks and objectives addressed by the bachelor thesis.

1.1 General

"Sonova is a leading global provider of innovative hearing solutions, ranging from personal audio devices and wireless communication solutions to audiological services, hearing aids and cochlear implants. Founded in 1947, the group is headquartered in Stäfa, Switzerland. Sonova operates in four business areas: hearing aids, audiological care, consumer hearing and cochlear implants. The group is represented in the market by its core brands Phonak, Unitron, AudioNova, Sennheiser (under licence) and Advanced Bionics, as well as regionally established brands. Through a broad global distribution network, Sonova serves a steadily growing number of customers in more than 100 countries." (Sonova AG, n.d.)

Sonova develops and distributes hearing aids and cochlear implants. Hearing tests are also required as part of these developments. The production of specific hearing tests is intended to be simplified in this work.

1.2 Initial situation and problem definition

In hearing research and the hearing device industry, psychoacoustic experiments are widely used to understand user behaviour and preferences. In order to be able to simulate hearing conditions as realistic as possible, experiment participants are often presented with audio material to increase realism and accuracy. This enables companies to evaluate in laboratories the performance of their devices in conditions that are representative of the conditions experienced by future users in real-life situations.

In order to be able to design such perceptual experiments, specific audio (and video footage) needs to be produced prior to the beginning of recording sessions. The content of these audios strongly depends on the hypothesis to be tested in the experiments, which means that previously available material often cannot be reused. The production of the audio sequences to be played during experiments is time-consuming and costly, depending also on the exact requirements. These requirements might include for example having many speakers with different voice characteristics or a large corpus of spoken sentences.

On the other hand, the quality of computer-generated media has increased dramatically in the last few years thanks to generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models. These include for example transformers, conformers and diffusion models, which have gained an increase in popularity thanks to tools such as Midjourney, Stable diffusion, ChatGPT, and many others.

1.3 Task description

This work will investigate the use of generative AI to produce synthetic audio material for psychoacoustic experiments, similarly to what is frequently seen on social media platforms in the form of so-called DeepFakes.

The focus will be on transforming everyday speech into raised-vocal-effort (Lombard) speech. This essentially means that a person will be able to record an audio where they speak normally. Using a tool, that recording will be converted to Lombard speech. Humans naturally adjust, for

example, their volume when it is very noisy in their surroundings. The goal is to list existing transformation methods to identify suitable objective evaluation metrics and then evaluate different methods for the conversion process. After finding the right tool, the next goal is to produce a listening test in collaboration with Sonova and to perform the subjective evaluation.

The thesis aims to complete the following goals:

1. Review of literature (find papers, tools, methods, datasets, etc.)
2. Define objective evaluation metrics
3. Select 2-3 methods/tools, re-implement them, and evaluate them.
4. Include a short listening test as part of the evaluation
5. Tests with subjective evaluation metrics (depending on availability from Sonova)

2 Current practice and state of technology

The following chapter provides an introduction to Lombard speech and discusses the current state of the technology.

2.1 Lombard speech

"The Lombard effect is an involuntary response speakers experience in the presence of noise during voice communication. This phenomenon is known to cause changes in speech production such as an increase in intensity, pitch structure, formant characteristics, etc. for enhanced audibility in noisy environments." (Lee et al., 2017)

As described in the literature, people speak differently when loud noise is present. This phenomenon has been studied for quite some time, but the conversion from normal to Lombard speech has not yet been examined in depth. As a result, it has not yet been possible to develop efficient and sufficient test results. These tests are essential in the hearing industry, for example, to design hearing aids for situations where Lombard speech is used.

In order to quantify Lombard speech, certain features are specifically considered:

- Fundamental frequency (F0)
- Sound pressure level (SPL)
- Vowel duration
- Spectral tilt
- Speech rate

When the vocal cords vibrate, they create a waveform that repeats at a certain rate. This rate, measured in Hertz (Hz), is the fundamental frequency (F0). For example, a waveform repeating 100 times per second has a fundamental frequency of 100 Hz.

Sound pressure levels are a logarithmic measure of the effective sound pressure of a sound wave relative to a reference value, expressed in decibels (dB). It quantifies the strength of a sound at a specific location, with higher SPL values indicating a louder sound.

The vowel duration is the length of a vowel sound in speech.

Spectral tilt refers to the slope of the speech spectrum, which describes the relative balance between low and high frequencies. A flatter tilt (less energy loss at higher frequencies) is associated with a louder or more "energetic" sound, while a steeper tilt (more high-frequency loss) sounds softer.

Speech rate is the speed at which a person speaks, commonly measured in words per minute (WPM).

Regarding Lombard speech, mostly an increase in F0, SPL, Vowel duration and Spectral tilt is measured, while the speech rate decreases. These values can differ, since many humans speak differently. SPL can be seen as the most evident speech attribute that changes between normal and Lombard speech. (Lee et al., 2017) (Garnier & Nathalie, 2013)

2.2 State of technology

Many different algorithms deal with language. The corresponding technical possibilities to execute such algorithms exist and are well developed. As of the writing of this thesis, unfortunately, no public pipelines are available yet.

Instead, this chapter focuses on explaining the technical fundamentals needed to understand the studies published so far in this field.

2.2.1 Machine learning

This thesis discusses machine learning models. Machine learning can help solve complex problems, such as understanding images and language. A model is an algorithm that learns by identifying patterns and then makes predictions based on the data it is fed. This learning process helps models to make accurate predictions and adapt through experience.

Here is how most of the fundamental learning processes work:

1. **Data Pre-processing:** the model needs data to analyse and learn properly. It is important that the data is of high quality. Furthermore, it is crucial that the amount of data is as high as possible to establish significant results. The data will be split into the following sets: training, validation, and test.
2. **Build a model:** an algorithm is a mathematical formula that processes data to find patterns. The most fitting algorithm should be chosen for a specific task. That algorithm will be defined as "the model". This algorithm must then be adapted to the task, for example, the type of inputs it receives and how it validates them.
3. **Model training:** There are different types of learning. The main goal of training is to have the model adjust its parameters to improve its predictions. It learns by computing the difference, also called error, between predictions and actual results and minimising those errors. The model compares predictions to the actual outcome. Subsequently, it uses this feedback to correct errors. In the training section, only the training and validation sets are used.
4. **Experience and Iteration:** training is repeated many times to refine the predictions. One fully completed training is called an iteration. To a certain degree, more iterations and more data improve prediction accuracy.
5. **Evaluation:** finally, the model is tested on the test set to evaluate its performance on real-world examples.

There are generally three major machine learning strategies for training a model: supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning is based on learning from labelled data. In this context, labelled means that each example in the dataset already includes the correct answer, also called "target value", that the model should learn to predict. Since most of the data in the Lombard topic is labelled, a supervised learning method is the most appropriate. (Hang, 2024)

2.2.2 Speaking style conversion from normal to Lombard speech using a glottal vocoder and Bayesian GMMs (2017)

The following study aims to analyse the performance of two vocoders using a Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model (BGMM). The chosen vocoders were STRAIGHT and a glottal vocoder. For an in-depth explanation of the model, the author refers to (Hang, 2024) and (Hill, 2018) for vocoder.

The dataset consisted of 10 Finnish speakers (4 females and 6 males), each reading a 90-word text, approximately 1 minute in duration. Once in normal and once in Lombard speech.

Figure 1: "Block diagram of the proposed speaking style conversion system. Prior to the conversion, the Bayesian Gaussian mixture models (GBMMs) are trained using pairs of normal and Lombard speech utterances." (Ana Ramirez et al., 2017)

The pipeline extracts different features of normal spoken language using the STRAIGHT Vocoder and the glottal vocoder. In both cases, the F0 was extracted using the REAPER tool. The durations were modified using cubic spline interpolation for all features of the two vocoders, except for the glottal vocoder's glottal excitation pulses, where nearest neighbour interpolation was applied.

For the mapping, the BGMMs were trained for each speaker and each vocoder feature using the corresponding spoken text. In the end, the pipeline re-synthesises using the predicted features.

Two evaluations were conducted. The first was a similarity comparison of the two converted Lombard speeches (using STRAIGHT and BGMM) and the natural Lombard speech. Listeners could rate on a scale of 1 to 5. For this purpose, 16 samples were taken randomly from the dataset. This meant that they had to evaluate both vocoder versions and rate 32 samples. The second evaluation was a pairwise comparison between the two generated Lombard speech files. In this case, the subjects listened to two versions of the same sentence. These were marked A and B. The testers had to choose which of the two sounded more natural. In this evaluation, 24 test cases were evaluated. The 24 utterances were taken randomly from the dataset.

According to the results of the study, the following analysis is made:

"Two subjective listening tests were employed to evaluate the conversion quality of the proposed system for the two vocoders. First, a similarity test evaluated the resemblance of the converted Lombard speech to natural Lombard speech. The results revealed that the conversion system was able to achieve conversion from normal to Lombard speech for the two vocoders. Both vocoders achieved the same level of resemblance to natural Lombard speech for female speakers. However, for male speakers, the glottal vocoder was rated higher in resemblance than STRAIGHT. A possible explanation for this is that male voices are generally easier to parameterize accurately with glottal vocoders than female voices due to their lower pitch, which makes the estimation of the glottal source with QCP more accurate. Second, a preference task compared the naturalness of the converted samples from both vocoders. The results showed that the converted samples obtained with the glottal vocoder were clearly more natural than those obtained with STRAIGHT [...]

[...] Finally, it should be noted that the similarity test results showed that the rate of resemblance to natural Lombard speech of the converted Lombard samples did not reach a high level for any of the vocoders. The difference between natural normal speech and natural Lombard speech is prominent and there are many acoustical properties that change from one style to another. In the present work, the features selected for conversion were spectral tilt, F0, energy, and duration. The changes in the vocal tract are also key in Lombard speech, but these were not included in the current system to maintain simplicity." (Ana Ramirez et al., 2017)

2.2.3 Vocal Effort Based Speaking Style Conversion Using Vocoder Features and Parallel Learning (2019)

This study uses a very similar approach but aims to provide a general speaking style conversion. They aim to compare three vocoders (GlottDNN, STRAIGHT, and the Pulse model in the log domain (PML)) with three machine learning mapping methods (standard GMM, Bayesian GMM, and feed-forward DNN). Refer to (Yuxi & Saransh, 2019) for an in-depth explanation of DNNs.

The dataset is the same as before and consists of 10 Finnish speakers (4 females and 6 males), each reading a 90-word text that lasts approximately 1 minute. Once normal and once in Lombard speech. They split the recordings into 11 lexically unique utterances. The duration of these utterances varied between 2 and 9 seconds. This way, the dataset consisted of 10 speakers, each speaking 11 sentences in both speaking styles, corresponding to a total of 220 utterances.

Figure 2: "Block diagram of the normal-to-Lombard SSC system. Prior to the conversion, the mapping models are trained using DTW aligned pairs of normal and Lombard speech utterances" (Shreyas et al., 2019)

Firstly, their pipeline extracts features from the source and target files. Since they had limited data, they chose to focus on the most critical features of Lombard, namely spectral tilt, F0, Energy, and duration. Then, a duration modification using dynamic time warp (DTW) was established. This modification is necessary because humans tend to speak more slowly in Lombard speech, and the signal parts would no longer match. In a real-world scenario, more vocal tract modifications would be needed in a pre-processing step, but since they had limited data, this step was skipped. They continue to feed the extracted features to the model. This way, the model can learn how these features differ and how they act. In the end, they re-synthesise using the predicted features. This pipeline was created with all nine combinations.

According to the results of the study, the following analysis is made:

"The results from the listening tests and the instrumental intelligibility tests show that DNNs created the largest Lombardness effect, although at the cost of perceived signal quality. In addition, SGMMs and BGMMs performed very similarly. This is an indication that the BGMMs are capable of handling overfitting without the expensive hyper-parameter tuning that is required for SGMMs [...]

[...] comparing the different vocoders, it was observed that GlottDNN is one of the best performing VOCs in terms of perceived quality but also leads to the smallest Lombardness score. This effect is also observable in the instrumental intelligibility tests where the GlottDNN has the

smallest improvement in comparison to the natural normal reference. STRAIGHT has a good balance between these two measures, and PML is the best in terms of Lombardness and the worst in terms of perceived quality." (Shreyas et al., 2019)

2.2.4 Elevenlabs

ElevenLabs is an artificial intelligence company specialising in speech synthesis and voice generation. The company launched its beta in 2023 and was founded by Piotr Dabkowski and Mati Staniszewski, with its headquarters in London. Its primary objective is to develop advanced AI models that generate natural-sounding human speech from text.

ElevenLabs' core products are based on deep neural network architectures for text-to-speech (TTS) synthesis. These systems typically combine large-scale transformer-based language models with neural vocoders to convert text into natural-sounding audio waveforms. The models are trained on extensive multilingual speech datasets, enabling the generation of speech with accurate prosody, intonation, emotional expression, and speaker identity.

The technology is widely applied in areas such as audiobook narration, video game development, film and media production, accessibility tools, education, and content creation. In addition to text-to-speech, ElevenLabs develops speech-to-speech and speech translation models, which preserve speaker-specific features while transforming linguistic content across languages. These models integrate automatic speech recognition (ASR), machine translation, and conditional speech synthesis within a unified pipeline.

Due to potential ethical concerns surrounding voice replication, ElevenLabs has implemented safeguards and usage policies to prevent misuse, including unauthorised voice impersonation. As a result, the company plays an important role not only in advancing speech synthesis technology but also in shaping discussions about ethical AI use and digital voice rights. (ElevenLabs, n.d.; Kanetkar, 2023)

3 Ideas and concepts

The following chapter addresses how the stated objectives of the work will be achieved. Rough ideas and approaches to solutions are outlined here. The specific steps for achieving the goals are explained in Chapter 5, "Implementation".

3.1 Literature review

The literature review is an ongoing process in this thesis. First and foremost, a basic understanding of signal processing and machine learning must be created. A critical part will be to identify studies, datasets, and methods for the desired implementation.

3.2 Define objective evaluation metrics

Since the project is audio-based, it is essential to establish objective metrics. Audio can sound and affect many people differently. The goal is to create a numerical value that objectively assesses a model's efficiency. There are various metrics for this; the ones suitable for the project should be selected and tested. A literature review will also be conducted for this purpose.

3.3 Select 2-3 methods/tools, re-implement them, and evaluate them.

The next step is to search for several suitable models. This essentially requires a search using related studies and the associated databases. Both open-source and commercial models can be used. If an appropriate method is described in a study but not implemented, it should be re-implemented.

Once the models have been selected, they should be evaluated using the predefined metrics. This will allow unsuitable models to be excluded immediately, and the process to continue.

3.4 Include a short listening test as part of the evaluation

In addition to the objective metrics, a subjective listening test will be conducted. This will be presented to acquaintances and fellow students to test the desired "Lombardness." The test will always be performed using the same headphones and laptop in a quiet room, so that the quality of different speakers does not influence the results. The test will be structured in a manner that participants are first presented with the generated file. Here, they should describe how natural and understandable the speech sounds. Then, the original "normal speech" file will be presented. Subsequently, they should explain how accurately the voice and articulation match the original. Finally, the original "Lombard speech" file will be presented. To sum up, they should describe how similar they sound.

3.5 Tests with subjective evaluation metrics (depending on availability from Sonova)

Sonova has requested that they also be allowed to test the results. Sonova will carry out the evaluations using subjective metrics. This will enable Sonova to influence the decision and assessment of the model. However, this evaluation will take place subject to availability.

4 Methods

The following chapter outlines the methods and procedures employed in the project.

4.1 Procedural model

The federal government uses the HERMES model for project management. This process model was chosen due to its modular structure and the experience already gained with HERMES.

«HERMES is the project management method for projects in the area of IT, service and product development, and business organization adjustment. HERMES supports the steering, management and execution of projects with various levels of complexity and different features. As a method, HERMES has a clear, easy-to-understand structure, has a modular design and can be expanded. The main method components and how they interact are described below.» (Admin.ch, n.d.-a)

The HERMES phase model shown in Figure 3 consists of four phases:

1. Initiation
2. Concept
3. Implementation
4. Deployment

Figure 3: The four phases of the HERMES phase model

(Admin.ch, n.d.-b)

The phases in the figure are now explained in relation to this project.

4.1.1 Initiation

During the initiation phase, the project objectives are defined, and the requirements are developed to the extent that concrete deliverables can be formed and evaluated. The task is created based on the selected deliverables.

Tasks description

The task description provides a brief outline of the initial situation and the problem. The objectives and expected results of the work are to be defined in consultation with the client. Additionally, the participants are identified here as the project team and the client. The formulated objectives can be found in Chapter 1.3.

Risk assessment

A risk analysis should also be carried out during this phase. Potential risks to the project are listed, and a risk map is created. Measures to minimise the extent of damage or the probability of occurrence are also listed.

Likelihood	Consequence				
	Insignificant 1	Minor 2	Moderate 3	Major 4	Catastrophic 5
Almost certain 5	9 5	10	15	20	25
Likely 4	4	8	12	6 16	20
Possible 3	3	6	8 9	3 12	4 15
Unlikely 2	2 2	1 4	7 6	5 8	10
Rare 1	1	2	3	4	5

Risk Outcome	Low	1-3
	Moderate	4-6
	Significant	5-12
	High	15-25

Figure 4: Risk map

The risk map is composed of the likelihood (L) and the consequences (C), which are explained in the further section of this chapter. The IDs of the risks are also shown in the table above. The risk map consists of two dimensions: on the left, the probability of occurrence (likelihood or frequency) is shown, scaled from 1 to 5. The higher this value, the more likely the corresponding consequence is to occur. On the other hand, the second dimension of the risk map shows the consequence and its impact on the matter (severity). If one combines these two dimensions, it is possible to set specific risks in terms of both frequency and severity.

The further down to the left the risk is positioned, the less likely its probability of occurrence. The severity of the risk is also very low. Such risks should by no means be ignored; however, when managed within risk management, they can lead to lower processing levels. In contrast, the further up to the right the risk is positioned, the more strongly it must be mitigated. Furthermore, such risks should be monitored and mitigated through appropriate measures.

Figure 5 shows the most important risks connected to this project and that have been defined as follows:

ID	Risk	L	C	Mitigation Strategy
1	Client is disrupted/not available	2	2	Organize substitute
2	Student is disrupted/not available	2	1	Plan enough buffer
3	Limited availability or accessibility of datasets	3	4	Identify datasets early
4	Quality of the Models are not enough (Poor generalization to different speakers or accents)	3	4	Evaluate multiple models. Fine-tune on small speaker sets
5	Limited computational resources for model training	2	4	Plan enough buffer/cloud GPU
6	Missing implementation details in literature or unavailable source code -> inconsistent software dependencies	4	4	Prioritize reproducible, open-source methods. Maybe contact authors
7	Delays in organizing listening test participants	2	3	Start recruitment early
8	Open-source tools or dependencies become unsupported	3	3	Use well-maintained libraries
9	Inconsistent test conditions across listening participants	4	2	Standardize playback instructions and use quality-check questions

Figure 5: Risk assessment

The analysis describes the project's risks, assesses the L and C, and outlines measures for each risk. The risks are based on personal assessments.

Risks 1 and 2 are typical. It is crucial to allow enough time and, if possible, to organise a substitute. Risks 3 to 6 were primarily selected because the thesis topic is particular and niche. Appropriate approaches were chosen to mitigate these risks. Finally, risks 7 to 9 were defined, as the evaluation and durability of the end product are essential to the work. It is crucial to plan the evaluation at an early stage, to provide the best possible instructions, and to use sustainable components.

In the last column, the corresponding mitigation strategies are shown. Thus, these strategies have been a crucial part of the risk management assessment for this thesis, helping keep disruptive risks to a minimum. Fortunately, the most implemented and defined risks related to this project were in the lower-left and middle sections of the risk map. This means that those risks were managed adequately without placing the entire bachelor's thesis in a high-risk regime.

4.1.2 Concept

In the concept phase, goal-oriented solution concepts are developed. Specifically, Chapter 3: "Ideas and Concepts" plays a crucial role in this project. It contains solution approaches for each goal of the thesis. These approaches are then implemented and explained in more detail in Chapter 5, Implementation.

Timetable

A schedule is also drawn up during this phase. This serves to keep track of planned progress. Additionally, 'checkpoints' are defined as points at which a meeting takes place between the main advisor and the student. The aim here is to generate joint feedback and, if necessary, to amend or even redefine the objectives at this stage.

Phase	Task	Start Date	End Date	KW	Comment
Initiation	Create Task description	15.09.25	29.09.25	38-40	
	Kick-Off Meeting	19.09.25	19.09.25	38	
Concept	Create timetable	26.09.25	02.10.25	40	
	1. Checkpoint	02.10.25	02.10.25	40	
	Create risk map	02.10.25	05.10.25	40	
Implementation	Literature review	06.10.25	30.11.25	40-48	Ongoing task. Steadily learning.
1. Milestone	Define objective evaluation metrics	06.10.25	26.10.25	41-43	
	2. Checkpoint	16.10.25	16.10.25	42	
	Find 2-3 tools to evaluate	27.10.25	09.11.25	44-45	
	3. Checkpoint	30.10.25	30.10.25	44	
2. Milestone	Utility analysis (Nutzwertanalyse)	10.11.25	16.11.25	46	
	4. Checkpoint	13.11.25	13.11.25	46	
	Train AI with datasets	17.11.25	30.11.25	47-48	
	5. Checkpoint	27.11.25	27.11.25	48	
	Create listening test	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
Deployment					
3. Milestone	Present listening test to colleagues	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
	Perform subjective tests with sonova	08.12.25	21.12.25	50-51	
4. Milestone	6. Checkpoint	11.12.25	11.12.25	50	
	Deadline BAA	05.01.26	05.01.26		

	Milestone is in timeline
	Milestone is slightly behind
	Milestone unattainable

Figure 6: Timetable from 30.09.25

The schedule provides an overview of the project progress. Work packages and milestones have been defined and specified. Achieving a milestone means that one or more project goals are simultaneously fulfilled.

4.1.3 Implementation

This phase describes the majority of the project. In this phase, the specific objectives are to be developed. This is where the definition of objective evaluation metrics, the selection of models and the execution of subjective evaluation should take place. The full implementation is described in Chapter 5.

4.1.4 Deployment

Finally, a subjective test should be conducted with Sonova to finalise the results. Once the subjective tests are complete, the project will enter the deployment phase. This involves discussing the results obtained in a final meeting and presenting the developed solution to conclude the project.

5 Implementation

The following chapter explains how the methods from Chapter 4 are applied to achieve the objectives outlined in Chapter 1.3.

5.1 Literature Review

5.1.1 Datasets

Four main datasets were identified in the literature review. All of the data in these datasets are labelled.

Audio-visual Lombard grid speech corpus

The first dataset is an English bi-view audio-visual Lombard speech corpus.

The corpus consists of 54 speakers: 30 female and 24 male. Each speaker has recorded 100 utterances, 50 in normal speech and 50 in Lombard speech, totalling 5400 audio files. The speakers listened to loud noises while recording, to trigger the Lombard effect.

The following is the format of the filenames:

SPKR_COND_UTTERANCE.wav e.g. s8_p_sbbi9p.wav

*SPKR = s1 to s55

*COND = l or p, where l -> Lombard, p -> plain (i.e. non-Lombard)

*UTTERANCE = 6-character Grid utterance code, e.g. "bbim3a" which means "bin blue in m 3 again"

The corpus had to be pre-processed because some errors were found in the utterance IDs. The corpus was therefore edited to ensure consistent naming and to retain only usable files. After selection, 5024 utterances remained. Additionally, the corpus also contains video recordings from the front and side for each utterance. (Najwa et al., 2018)

An enhanced Mandarin Lombard Grid Corpus with Meaningful Sentences (EMALG)

The second dataset is an extension of the Mandarin Lombard Grid (MALG). The study connected to this dataset reveals that, in Mandarin, meaningful sentences are more effective at enhancing the Lombard effect.

The corpus consists of 34 speakers: 17 females and 17 males. All participants were native Mandarin speakers and had passed a Mandarin proficiency test at Level 2 or higher. Each speaker has recorded 100 complete sentences in three different speech levels, totalling 10'200 audio files. The speakers were listening to three different noise levels (40/55/80dB) to create different Lombard effects.

The following explains the format of the filenames:

GSPKR_ID_NOISE_1_C.wav|.lab e.g. F152_U006_SSN40_1_C.wav

*G = F or M, where F -> female, M -> male

*SPKR = Speaker ID

*ID = Unique sentence ID for each speaker, e.g. U006 to U105

*NOISE= Noise level, e.g. SSN40, SSN55, SSN80

(Li et al., 2023)

The Berlin Dataset of Lombard and Masked Speech (BELMASK)

The third dataset consists of 10 German native speakers: 4 females and 6 males. It contains a total of 128 minutes of audio and video recordings of uttering sentences in cued, uninstructed speech across four conditions: with a Filtering Facepiece P2 (FFP2) mask, without an FFP2 mask, with an FFP2 mask while exposed to noise, and without an FFP2 mask while exposed to noise. The speakers listened to mixed-gender six-talker babble through headphones to trigger the Lombard effect.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to access this dataset, as the files are restricted to authorised users. File access was requested, but no authorisation was granted.

(Moshona et al., 2024)

Nijmegen Corpus of Lombard Speech

The fourth dataset consists of 42 Dutch speakers: 37 females and 5 males. Each speaker recorded a folk story of 56 utterances, both in normal and Lombard speech. The speakers listened to white noise to trigger the Lombard effect. Recordings that had been evaluated as inaccurate by the experimenter, together with the matching plain or Lombard counterpart recording of that speaker, were excluded. After the evaluation, 3968 audio files remained.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to access this dataset either, as the dataset was not available online.

(Bosker & Cooke, 2020)

The French Lombard Dataset

The fifth dataset consists of 38 French speakers: 19 females and 19 males. Each speaker has recorded 60 sentences selected from the "Fharvard" database at four increasing levels of vocal intensity, totalling 9'120 audio files. The speakers listened to four different levels of white noise (0, 65, 75 and 85 dB) to trigger various Lombard effects.

The following explains the format of the filenames:

NN_SN_LN_XXXX_YYYYYY

*NN = Speaker ID

*SN = Session ID

*LN = List ID of the Fharvard corpus, e.g. "l3" refers to list number 3.

*XXXX = Sentence ID of the Fharvard corpus, e.g. "sent8" refers to the sentence 8.

*YYYYYY = Noise condition, i.e., noise0, noise1, noise2 and noise3 for 0, 65, 75 and 85 dB, respectively.

(Jacquelin et al., 2025)

5.2 Objective evaluation metrics

In order to define objective metrics, it is crucial to consider the context of use. In this case, it is needed for comparing two audio files in which speech is analysed. All of these metrics are used in this thesis as quantitative metrics to evaluate the quality of the generated speech. Mel-cepstral distance (MCD), Spectral Cross-Correlation (SCC), Hearing Aid Speech Perception Index (HASPI), and Hearing Aid Speech Quality Index (HASQI) were used for this purpose. All of these metrics were combined into a single Python file using ChatGPT.

5.2.1 Mel-Cepstral Distance

The Mel-Cepstral Distance (MCD) is a speech quality measure designed to improve upon the Cepstral Distance by incorporating perceptual characteristics of human hearing. (R., 2025)

The Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) are defined as:

$$MCx(i, k) = \sum_{n=1}^M X_{k,n} \cos\left(i\left(n - \frac{1}{2}\right)\frac{\pi}{M}\right)$$

Figure 7: Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (Stefan & Jasmin, 2025)

where:

- M is the number of coefficients,
- $MCx(i, k)$ denotes the i -th MFCC for the k -th frame,
- $X_{k,n}$ denotes the Mel-scaled power spectrogram for the k -th frame.

The MCD for the k -th frame is given by:

$$MCD(k) = a \sqrt{\sum_{i=s}^D (MCx(i, k) - MCy(i, k))^2}$$

Figure 8: Mel-cepstral distance per frame (Stefan & Jasmin, 2025)

where:

- $MCx(i, k)$ denotes the MFCC of the reference signal,
- $MCy(i, k)$ denotes the MFCC of the target signal,
- a , s , and D are constants described in (R., 2025)

The MCD is then defined as the average of $MCD(k)$ over all frames:

$$MCD = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N MCD(k)$$

Figure 9: Mean over all frames (Stefan & Jasmin, 2025)

where:

- N is the total number of frames.

5.2.2 Spectral Cross-Correlation

Cross-Correlation is a measure of similarity between two signals as one is shifted relative to the other. It quantifies how well one signal aligns with shifted versions of another signal. To evaluate the spectral similarity between a recorded syllable and the corresponding synthesized syllable, the cross-correlation of their magnitude spectrograms is computed.

The discrete-time cross-correlation for two one-dimensional signals of length N is defined as:

$$z[k] = \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} x[l] \overline{y[l - k + N - 1]}$$

Figure 10: Discrete-time Cross-correlation

where:

- $k = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$
- $y[m] = 0$ for $m \notin \{0, 1, \dots, N - 1\}$

5.2.3 Hearing Aid Speech Perception Index & Hearing Aid Speech Quality Index

HASPI and HASQI are objective metrics developed to predict how hearing-aid processing affects speech intelligibility (HASPI) and speech quality (HASQI). Both metrics use a computational model of an impaired auditory system to estimate how a listener with sensorineural hearing loss would perceive a processed speech signal and share the same foundational steps:

1. Two signals are compared:
 - a. A clean reference signal
 - b. A processed signal (e.g., after hearing-aid processing, noise reduction, compression)
2. Both signals are passed through an auditory model. This model simulates:
 - a. Outer/middle ear filtering
 - b. Cochlear frequency analysis
 - c. Impaired auditory compression
 - d. Temporal-envelope extraction
 - e. Internal noise and reduced dynamic range

This step converts the raw waveforms into internal auditory representations resembling what a hearing-impaired listener would detect.

3. Correlation-based comparison

Perceptually relevant features (envelopes, temporal fine structure, distortion measures) are compared between clean and processed representations.

HASPI – Intelligibility Metric

HASPI focuses on two components:

1. Envelope fidelity
 - a. Compares slow amplitude fluctuations in individual frequency bands
 - b. Critical for consonant/vowel cues and phoneme boundaries
2. Fine-structure fidelity
 - a. Compares rapid temporal fluctuations
 - b. Related to voicing cues and harmonic structure

Both contributions are combined into a final score between 0 and 1, where:

- 1 = perfectly intelligible
- 0 = unintelligible

(James M. & Kathryn H., 2022)

Figure 11: Block diagram showing the steps involved in the HASPI calculation (James M. & Kathryn H., 2022)

HASQI – Quality Metric

HASQI analyses distortions introduced by hearing-aid processing. It quantifies:

1. Linear distortions
 - a. Changes in frequency response
 - b. Bandwidth limitations
 - c. Linear filtering effects
2. Nonlinear distortions
 - a. Compression artifacts
 - b. Clipping
 - c. Temporal smoothing
 - d. Envelope distortions
3. Temporal and spectral fidelity
 - a. Measures whether timing/spectral details match the clean signal in the auditory domain

The output is again 0 to 1, as already mentioned, 1 = perfectly intelligible and 0 = unintelligible.

(James M. & Kathryn H., 2022)

Figure 12: Block diagram showing the steps involved in the HASQI calculation (James M. & Kathryn H., 2022)

5.3 Implementation from the study

The first approach in the implementation was to try to implement one of the pipelines from the study (Shreyas et al., 2019). The results show that the DNN produced the most significant Lombardness effect and that the STRAIGHT Vocoder achieved a good balance between perceived quality and Lombardness. For this reason, the best option would be to use the combination of the Vocoder STRAIGHT and the DNN as the model.

Unfortunately, STRAIGHT is distributed chiefly as MATLAB code, and the model was saved as a ".mat" file. At the time of trying, there was no access to the MATLAB environment. Therefore, a small own pipeline was created in Python using a successor to STRAIGHT called WORLD, and the model was converted to a ".h5"-File.

The pipeline was intended to work the same way as described in the study. The vocoder extracts the features F0, spectral envelope and aperiodicity. The DNN consisted of 4 hidden layers with 250 neurons each. The weights were initialised from the pre-trained DNN.

```
[C:\Users\lenny> python D:/Git_repos/Study/speech_regression/make_pytrain_from_audio.py C:/Users/lenny/Downloads/lombardgrid_audio_s2/lombardgrid/s2_p_bbin3a.wav C:/Users/lenny/Downloads/lombardgrid_audio_s2/lombardgrid/s2_1_bbin3a.wav D:/Git_repos/Study/speech_regression/tmpFiles/DNN_model_converted.h5 D:/Git_repos/Study/speech_regression/tmpFiles]
[INFO] Extracting features...
[INFO] src features: (156, 3), tgt features: (174, 3)
[INFO] Aligning with DTW...
[INFO] aligned shapes: src=(216, 3), tgt=(216, 3)
[INFO] Split: train=172 frames, predict=44 frames
[INFO] Writing pytrain.py to: D:/Git_repos/Study/speech_regression/tmpFiles/pyTrain.py
[OK] pyTrain.py written.
```

Figure 13: First Test creation of a file containing the features

Firstly, three train files were created with a corpus builder script:

- world_train.npz (Train set)
- world_dev.npz (Validation set)
- world_test.npz (Test set)

These three files contained the numerical values of the extracted features. The corpus builder randomly selected utterances to fit into these three files. The training split for this was 70% training, 15% validation and 15% test. The vocoder extracted these features using the default WORLD frame shift of 5 ms. The compression sizes varied during testing between 60 and 120 for the spectral envelope and between 5 and 10 for the aperiodicity.

For training, multiple values were also chosen. Epochs ranged from 5 to 30, with batch sizes of 256 or 512. The learning rate was tested over a range of $3e-5$ to $1e-4$. The dropout rate was chosen based on whether the model seemed to be overfitting.

In the end, a test was conducted in which one normal spoken file was given as input. However, the model did not produce a satisfying result. One approach to solving this issue was to synthesise multiple files using only one predicted feature and the ground truth for the others, though this didn't succeed either.

Figure 14: Generated files using predicted and ground truth values for synthesising.

5.4 Self-experiment

After evaluating the situation, a self-experiment was conducted. This experiment would be to create everything anew and see how the results would behave. The pipeline is still the same, but now using a Librosa vocoder and a newly created DNN with a convolutional LSTM.

The vocoder now extracts F0, mel-spectrogram and energy. The DNN consisted of 83 input and 80 output dimensions, and 3 to 4 hidden layers with 256 neurons each, with a dropout rate of 0.1.

First, a script is created that generates a .json file mapping each normal spoken file to its corresponding Lombard file. For this experiment, 90% of the files were in the train set and 10% in the test set.

The training was done using PyTorch. The only values edited during training were the epochs, which ranged from 1 to 30, and the batch size, which was either 128, 256, or 512. The script created a checkpoint model every 10 epochs. The script also normalised the dataset into a .npz file.

The final test was conducted using a single input file and resynthesizing, utilising the model's predictions. Although the model again did not produce a satisfactory result, there was an audible improvement in perceived quality when varying the number of epochs and the dataset size.

5.5 Baseline

To try to approximate the Lombard speech, a baseline was established. The baseline included changing the volume and pitch of a file.

A first version of the script was created using ChatGPT for the audio-visual Lombard grid speech corpus. It was then edited to fit the project.

The script parses all plain files marked with the letter "p" in the input folder and applies the volume change in dB and the pitch change in semitones. After processing, it saves the file with the text "_proc" appended to its name to the output folder. Now it loads all files marked with the letter "l" and computes the objective evaluation metrics using their corresponding "p" files. The MCD is computed using the mel-cepstral-distance repository (Stefan & Jasmin, 2025). The

repository was edited, so the function now takes a path to the audio file rather than the audio file itself. The SCC is computed directly in the script, and HASPI/HASQI is computed using the PyClarity repository (The PyClarity Team, 2025). At the end, the script prints all computed metrics to the terminal for each pair, along with the average across all pairs.

```

(.venv) PS D:\Git_BAA\Evaluations_all> python.exe .\compare.py .\test\ 5.0 0.5 -o .\out\
Input dir   : D:\Git_BAA\Evaluations_all\test
Output dir  : .\out\
Gain (dB)   : 5.0
Pitch (st)  : 0.5

Pair: s2_p_bbim3a.wav vs s2_l_bbim3a.wav
MCD (dB)    : 6.6060
Spectral Corr : 0.9179
HASPI       : 0.25546063262518837
HASQI       : 0.052825273244395655

```

Figure 15: Terminal input for the baseline and computation for the metrics for one pair

```

===== Overall summary =====
Number of pairs: 50
Mean MCD           : 6.2624 dB
Mean Spectral Corr : 0.9542
Mean HASPI         : 0.5274
Mean HASQI         : 0.1518
=====

```

Figure 16: Terminal output for the computation across all pairs

The figures above show examples of the quantitative metrics output in the terminal.

5.6 ElevenLabs

To test the tool, the author's voice was cloned. This step was done once speaking normally and once speaking in Lombard speech for 2 minutes each. To trigger the Lombard effect, a loud audio of restaurant noise was played over the headphones while speaking. The voices are labelled "L_Normal" and "L_Lombard".

After cloning, two samples with the sentence "*I hope you can hear me*" were created using the two voices. For the normal spoken sentence, the text was written plain, and no prompts were used. The Lombard sentence was written in capital letters, and the prompt "[speak loudly]" was given. These samples yielded promising results and were presented to Sonova. Therefore, it was decided to work onward with ElevenLabs.

Figure 17: Screenshot of the ElevenLabs TTS interface

Throughout the testing of the tool, a few observations were made:

- The tool can take prompts as input to express emotions using square brackets "[]".
- Punctuations make a difference in expression.
- Writing a text in capital letters also affects the expression.

To establish the subjective evaluation, four additional voices were cloned from two speakers of the audio-visual Lombard grid speech corpus. All the 50 normal spoken utterances were given as input for the "Normal voices" and the other 50 for the "Lombard voices". The voices were labelled as "S2_Normal", "S2_Lombard", "S27_Normal" and "S27_Lombard".

For each of these voices, the following samples were created:

- Normal: The input was standard text, with no prompts.
- Loudly: The input was standard text, with the prompt "[speak loudly]".
- Very loudly in capital letters: The input was written in capital letters, with the prompt "[speak very loudly]".
- Shout: The input was standard text, with the prompt "[shout]".

5.7 Subjective evaluation

Sonova conducted the subjective evaluation via the Soundsurvey website. The requirement for a successful computation of the results was that all samples must be the same length and have the same sampling rate. Therefore, all samples were zero-padded to the same length and saved at the same sampling rate.

A normalisation of volume was also needed, as the original samples were quieter than the generated ones. This step was done manually using the Audacity tool, by calculating the difference of the Root Mean Square (RMS) between the original and generated pairs (Normal and Lombard).

After processing, the samples were uploaded to the Soundsurvey website. For each speaker, all of the following samples were chosen to be uploaded:

- Recorded original normal speech
- Recorded original Lombard speech
- Processed Baseline

- Generated normal speech using the normal voice
- Generated loud speech using the Lombard voice
- Generated very loud speech in capital letters using the normal voice and Lombard voice
- Generated shout speech using the Lombard voice

Users were instructed to use a pair of headphones (if possible) and how to rate the samples. The samples were presented in a randomised and anonymised order. Users had to listen to all the samples on a single page before proceeding to the next. The rating was done using a slider with three sections: Normal speech, loud speech, and very loud speech. The Users had to approximate the slider to the most fitting section.

Figure 18: Screenshot of the subjective evaluation on the Soundsurvey website

6 Validation and Evaluation

The following chapter evaluates the objectives defined in Chapter 1.3. A comparison is made to determine whether these objectives have been achieved.

The initial objective of this thesis was to find and evaluate a speech-to-speech system to create synthetic Lombard data. Throughout the project's lifespan, the goal shifted toward text-to-speech due to minimal literature. The thesis aims to be a compilation of available literature, experiments and findings towards the initial goal. It includes a workaround solution using the ElevenLabs tool to create a speech-to-text-to-speech system.

6.1 Goal 1 – Review of literature

As a result of this phase of the work, a fundamental understanding of signal processing and machine learning relevant to speech-to-speech systems was established. In addition, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify suitable objective evaluation metrics, along with the corresponding methods and tools. This review served as a baseline for the subsequent stages of the thesis and enabled the definition and completion of the following goals. Therefore, the work done so far is consistent with the established goals.

6.2 Goal 2 – Define objective evaluation metrics

Mel-cepstral distance (MCD), spectral cross-correlation (SCC), hearing-aid speech perception index (HASPI), and hearing-aid speech quality index (HASQI) were selected as objective evaluation metrics. MCD and SCC are well-established metrics commonly used in the field of signal processing, whereas HASPI and HASQI originate from research on hearing aids and speech intelligibility and quality.

At the time of writing this thesis, no dedicated objective metric existed for directly quantifying the Lombard effect or the "Lombardness" of a speech signal. One existing approach uses signal-to-noise ratio-based evaluations, which are also relevant in the context of Lombard speech. This approach involves presenting background noise alongside the speech signal and assessing its audibility. While such a method may provide indirect insights into Lombard characteristics, it does not yield a clear or explicit metric for measuring Lombardness. Therefore, the work done so far is consistent with the established goals.

6.3 Goal 3 – Select 2-3 methods/tools, re-implement them, and evaluate them

Unfortunately, no direct speech-to-speech systems were found during the search for suitable methods/tools. Some systems are not publicly available and cannot be evaluated within the scope of this work (see chapter 2.2). The authors of the respective studies were contacted, but this did not lead to any results.

Current studies are still mainly concerned with research into Lombard speech itself. Most approaches to synthesis focus primarily on text-to-speech. Many approaches also pursue the idea of transfer learning. This means that an already established text-to-speech system, such as Tacotron, is used, with Lombard data fed into it. In this way, what the model has already learned can be directed in a specific direction. For example, refer to: (Bajibabu et al., 2019; Qiong et al., 2021)

To approximate Lombard speech, a baseline transformation was established. This baseline changes the volume and pitch of the voice.

```

===== Overall summary =====
Number of pairs: 2504
Mean MCD           : 7.2182 dB
Mean Spectral Corr : 0.7582
Mean HASPI         : 0.2609
Mean HASQI         : 0.0474
=====

```

Figure 19: Summary of the baseline transformation evaluation before the transformation

```

===== Overall summary =====
Number of pairs: 2504
Mean MCD           : 7.7811 dB
Mean Spectral Corr : 0.7878
Mean HASPI         : 0.2950
Mean HASQI         : 0.0600
=====

```

Figure 20: Summary of the baseline transformation evaluation when increasing by 5 dB and 0.5 semitones

The parameters selected for the transformation were 5 dB and 0.5 semitones. These parameters were declared the most successful in smaller tests. As shown in Figures 19 and 20, there was an improvement in average scores for SCC, HASPI, and HASQI.

Ultimately, a text-to-speech system was found that enables an audible Lombard effect. In Elevenlabs, prompts can be used to create specific expressions, such as Lombard speech. It is even possible to input audio files to clone a voice. This would make the system a speech-to-text-to-speech system. Therefore, the work done so far is consistent with the established goals.

6.4 Goal 4 – Include a short listening test as part of the evaluation

The original goal of including a subjective evaluation was to assess the various methods/tools. Ultimately, however, only one solution was applied in the thesis. Accordingly, a set of samples was created for Sonova to conduct a subjective review. The result of the review was positive, and therefore, it was decided to continue with ElevenLabs. Therefore, the work done so far is consistent with the established goals.

6.5 Goal 5 – Tests with subjective evaluation metrics

The evaluation was conducted over a week using the Soundsurvey platform. During this time, 20 participants completed the survey. Participants were instructed to rate the audio files based on how loud the speaker was trying to speak. The higher the value, the louder or more forceful the speaker's voice was.

Three speakers were selected during the evaluation. The author's voice was cloned for the "L subject". Speakers from the Audio-Visual Lombard Grid Speech Corpus were chosen for the "s2 subject" and "s27 subject" voices. It was taken into consideration to ensure that the speakers had different levels of Lombard effects. It is audibly highest in the L subject and audibly lowest in the S2 subject.

The sample names display in their first word if they are either generated or recorded, i.e. "gen" or "rec". The second word describes the vocal effort of the sample, i.e. "normal" or "Lombard". The third word represents the prompt given, and if the sentence was written in capital letters, e.g. "veryloudlycaps".

In this chapter, a descriptive analysis of the results is first presented, followed by a quantitative analysis. For an in-depth explanation of ANOVA or T-Tests, refer to (Newbold et al., 2019)

Figure 21: Screenshot of the results for the L subject on the Soundsurvey website

For the L subject, the perceived Lombard effect was highest in the original files. Looking at the box plots for the L subject, it can be seen that the ElevenLabs-generated files were also evaluated as expected. In a comparison between "gen normal normal" and "rec normal," they performed very similarly. The next highest was the baseline transformation with "proc baseline." It can also be seen that the selected prompts and letters seem to contribute, as the normal spoken voice was rated higher when the prompt "speak very loudly" was used and when written in capital letters. Furthermore, it can be seen that ElevenLabs achieved a similar result with the Lombard voice as the original recorded Lombard file. Ultimately, there seems to be an overlap between the generated Lombard voices with the prompts "shout" and "speak very loudly" written in capital letters.

Figure 22: Screenshot of the results for the S2 subject on the Soundsurvey website

The S2 subject was selected because of the low perceived Lombard effect in the original files. Compared to the other subjects, it had the lowest Lombard effect. This fact is also reflected in the survey results. It appears that there is substantial overlap across almost all samples. The samples "gen normal normal" and "gen Lombard shoutcaps" exhibit the most significant deviation.

Figure 23: Screenshot of the results for the S27 subject on the Soundsurvey website

The S27 subject was chosen as a middle ground between the L subject and the S2 subject in terms of the Lombard effect, and since it is a female voice. It should be noted that "rec normal," "proc baseline," and "gen normal normal" have a considerable overlap. Accordingly, ElevenLabs has created similar results with this speaker. In addition, "rec Lombard," "gen Lombard loudly," "gen Lombard veryloudly," and "gen normal veryloudlycaps" also performed very similarly. The highest-rated sample is "gen Lombard shoutcaps." It can therefore be assumed that a high Lombard effect can be achieved with this speaker, but most prompts have no significant impact, except for the "shout" prompt with capital letters.

The next tables show an overview of the significances when comparing the results of two samples.

Table 1: Pairwise T-Test of the L subject

L subject	zeroPadded_L_Lombard_Loudly.wav	zeroPadded_L_Lombard_Original.wav	zeroPadded_L_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_L_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_L_Normal_Normal.wav	zeroPadded_L_Normal_Original_proc.wav	zeroPadded_L_Normal_Original.wav
zeroPadded_L_Lombard_Original.wav	5.46e-02 ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_L_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	2.94e-13 ****	1.99e-23 ****	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_L_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	2.02e-10 ****	5.43e-20 ****	1.00e+00 ns	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_L_Normal_Normal.wav	5.40e-30 ****	5.50e-19 ****	5.95e-61 ****	3.73e-57 ****	-	-	-
zeroPadded_L_Normal_Original_proc.wav	3.86e-23 ****	5.14e-13 ****	1.07e-53 ****	7.37e-50 ****	1.00e+00 ns	-	-
zeroPadded_L_Normal_Original.wav	3.73e-33 ****	7.41e-22 ****	3.75e-64 ****	2.21e-60 ****	1.00e+00 ns	1.74e-01 ns	-
zeroPadded_L_Normal_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	6.91e-12 ****	2.37e-04 ***	3.38e-40 ****	2.20e-36 ****	3.35e-06 ****	1.41e-02 *	3.38e-08 ****

Significance codes: > 0.05 ' ns = not significant ', ≤ 0.05 ' * ', ≤ 0.01 ' ** ', ≤ 0.001 ' *** ', ≤ 0.0001 ' **** '

When analysing the table, it becomes apparent that a highly significant difference is measured in almost all cases. When comparing "Lombard Original" and "Lombard loudly," the difference is not significant. This leads to the conclusion that the prompt "speak loudly" does not create a statistically significant difference in perceived Lombardness using the L subject. This can also be seen between "Lombard veryloudly" in capital letters and "Lombard shout" in caps. In the baseline transformation, there was also no significant difference between the generated "normal normal" and the recorded "normal original". This suggests that the baseline transformation does not offer any improvement in terms of Lombardness for the L subject. Finally, it can be seen that there is no significant difference between "normal original" and "normal normal." This means that ElevenLabs has created a very similar copy of the original with the L subject.

Table 2: Pairwise T-Test of the S2 subject

S2 subject	zeroPadded_s2_l_bwbo8a.wav	zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_Loudly.wav	zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_S2_Normal_Normal.wav	zeroPadded_S2_Normal_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_s2_p_bwbo8a_proc.wav
zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_Loudly.wav	2.53e-01 ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	1.76e-04 ***	1.10e-10 ****	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S2_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	1.00e+00 ns	9.01e-04 ***	8.09e-02 ns	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S2_Normal_Normal.wav	7.29e-04 ***	1.00e+00 ns	1.69e-15 ****	3.28e-07 ****	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S2_Normal_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	1.00e+00 ns	6.25e-02 ns	1.26e-03 **	1.00e+00 ns	9.77e-05 ****	-	-
zeroPadded_s2_p_bwbo8a_proc.wav	1.00e+00 ns	4.00e-04 ***	1.46e-01 ns	1.00e+00 ns	1.15e-07 ****	1.00e+00 ns	-
zeroPadded_s2_p_bwbo8a.wav	1.18e-01 ns	1.00e+00 ns	2.16e-11 ****	3.01e-04 ***	1.00e+00 ns	2.65e-02 *	1.29e-04 ***

Significance codes: > 0.05 ' ns = not significant ', ≤ 0.05 ' * ', ≤ 0.01 ' ** ', ≤ 0.001 ' *** ', ≤ 0.0001 ' **** '

Since the S2 subject had a low perceived Lombard effect, the samples were also evaluated accordingly. The table shows that, compared to the L subject, more values are calculated as not significant. This shows that using a voice with a high Lombard effect yields more significant and accurate results.

Table 3: Pairwise T-Test of the S27 subject

S27 subject	zeroPadded_s27_lbwr9p.wav	zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_Loudly.wav	zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_S27_Normal_Normal.wav	zeroPadded_S27_Normal_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	zeroPadded_s27_p_lbwr9p_proc.wav
zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_Loudly.wav	1.00e+00 ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_Shout_Caps.wav	5.93e-03 **	7.10e-04 ***	-	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S27_Lombard_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	1.00e+00 ns	1.00e+00 ns	4.05e-01 ns	-	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S27_Normal_Normal.wav	1.97e-10 ****	4.86e-09 ****	3.90e-22 ****	3.89e-14 ****	-	-	-
zeroPadded_S27_Normal_VeryLoudly_Caps.wav	8.65e-01 ns	1.00e+00 ns	2.42e-07 ****	1.74e-02 *	3.22e-05 ****	-	-
zeroPadded_s27_p_lbwr9p_proc.wav	8.97e-09 ****	1.79e-07 ****	5.52e-20 ****	2.83e-12 ****	1.00e+00 ns	5.62e-04 ***	-
zeroPadded_s27_p_lbwr9p.wav	6.39e-17 ****	2.92e-15 ****	5.84e-30 ****	3.41e-21 ****	8.31e-01 ns	1.77e-10 ****	1.45e-01 ns

Significance codes: > 0.05 ' ns = not significant ', ≤ 0.05 ' * ', ≤ 0.01 ' ** ', ≤ 0.001 ' *** ', ≤ 0.0001 ' **** '

Looking at the results of the S27, it can be seen that ElevenLabs created distinct samples. It is worth noting that when comparing the "loudly", "veryloudlycaps", and "rec lombard" files, there was no significance between them.

After finishing the evaluation and discussing the results with Sonova, the completed work is marked as consistent with the established goals.

7 Outlook

The following chapter presents a solution-oriented and critical self-reflection, a reflection on the project and recommends actions that Sonova can take for further proceedings. Furthermore, this outlook also identifies potential future research topics and/or enhancements. Upon completion of the project, Sonova will have a functional conversion tool that the student has tested and can use to perform additional experiments or research.

7.1 Reflection

Initially, the author signed up for a different topic. However, since that didn't work out, he came across this project. The interest in the subject was high, but he had minimal experience in the field. The author was keen to complete this project successfully and provide a valuable solution and contribution to both Sonova and science. This thesis especially aims to provide a foundation for future research.

Accordingly, the learning curve was immense. During the project, the author explored the fundamentals of signal processing and machine learning. It was an exciting experience to immerse himself so deeply in a new field and learn from it. The working method of research was also new to the author. This overall was an extensive educational experience.

The bachelor's thesis provided insight into the methodology and structure of academic work and serves as a solid foundation for future endeavours. It also serves as valuable preparation for practical work in the professional world. In addition, the thesis lays a foundation to the author for further academic work, such as the persuasion of a master's degree in cyber security.

Initially, there was a challenge with the author's specialist knowledge. This was overcome in the first few weeks through intensive self-experimentation. Small pipelines were created to develop a basic understanding of the subject area. In the process, the author gained many insights for the project.

It quickly became clear that the literature was still incomplete at the time of writing and would not be sufficient to complete the project. It was essential to thoroughly examine the available resources and learn as much as possible from them. A lot of experimentation was done, and then an approximation attempt was started using baselines.

In this part of the project, the author became unsure about its course. It felt as if there was no longer a clear goal. However, with the advisor's and the client's help, it was possible to continue working in one direction. In the end, a satisfactory solution was found. This resulted in a clear goal and, with it, great joy and motivation. The author did everything in his power to achieve this goal and complete the project successfully.

Out of the 5 defined goals, 4 were consistent with the completed work. It was imperative to the author to accomplish the goals flawlessly. The reason for this was to complete the bachelor's project to a high standard, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Nevertheless, more extensive specialist knowledge of the subject areas would have led to faster, more diverse solutions. In the future, an intensive preparation phase should be considered.

7.2 Recommendations for action

The author presents the most important recommendations for action below, which are advice for future implementations:

First and foremost, a comprehensive speech-to-speech synthesis system should be available. To this end, it would be possible to contact the author of the 2019 study and await his answer when more time is available. If a direct speech-to-speech model becomes available in the future, it would be possible to train using the speech-to-text-to-speech system and establish it for synthesis accordingly. Until then, the baseline transformation could be improved. The use of a neural vocoder could be helpful here.

It would also be possible to create a standalone model, but this would require access to many data sets to ensure sufficient data for training. The ElevenLabs solution could also be used here to generate synthetic data. It should be noted that a female voice generally has a flatter spectral tilt. Therefore, more testing using female voices would be helpful as well.

In order to determine the Lombardness of future signals, the use of the signal-to-noise ratio could prove helpful. A model could also be used here in which the characteristics of Lombard speech have been learned, and which can analyse a signal for these characteristics accordingly.

8 Appendices

All additional documents that were supplied are listed below. Excel files have been inserted as images in the respective chapters. The various versions of the timetable have also been included.

Additional documents supplied:

Web-Abstract

Pitching Video

8.1 Pairwise T-tests

This table shows the pairwise T-test across all samples in the survey, provided by Sonova.

Overall-Analysis	gen lombard loudly	gen lombard shoutcaps	gen lombard veryloudlycaps	gen normal normal	gen normal veryloudlycaps	proc baseline	rec lombard
gen lombard shoutcaps	2.53e-01 ns	-	-	-	-	-	-
gen lombard veryloudlycaps	1.76e-04 ***	1.10e-10 ****	-	-	-	-	-
gen normal normal	1.00e+00 ns	9.01e-04 ***	8.09e-02 ns	-	-	-	-
gen normal veryloudlycaps	7.29e-04 ***	1.00e+00 ns	1.69e-15 ****	3.28e-07 ****	-	-	-
proc baseline	1.00e+00 ns	6.25e-02 ns	1.26e-03 **	1.00e+00 ns	9.77e-05 ****	-	-
rec lombard	1.00e+00 ns	4.00e-04 ***	1.46e-01 ns	1.00e+00 ns	1.15e-07 ****	1.00e+00 ns	-
rec normal	1.18e-01 ns	1.00e+00 ns	2.16e-11 ****	3.01e-04 ***	1.00e+00 ns	2.65e-02 *	1.29e-04 ***

Significance codes: > 0.05 ' ns = not significant ', ≤ 0.05 ' * ', ≤ 0.01 ' ** ', ≤ 0.001 ' *** ', ≤ 0.0001 ' **** '

8.2 ANOVA

This table shows the ANOVA statistics of the survey, provided by Sonova. The following labels are used:

SystemLabel = number of audio files

Sample = number of speakers

UserName = number of participants

Replicate = number of iterations of the survey

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
SystemLabel	7	366529.5	52361.36	209.06	3.89e-172 ****
Sample	2	51298.72	25649.36	102.41	4.34e-40 ****
UserName	19	94234.64	4959.72	19.8	3.23e-54 ****
Replicate	1	114.13	114.13	0.46	5.00e-01 ns
SystemLabel:Sample	14	99675.19	7119.66	28.43	2.68e-60 ****
SystemLabel:UserName	133	77114.52	579.81	2.31	1.75e-12 ****
SystemLabel:Replicate	7	1239.98	177.14	0.71	6.66e-01 ns
UserName:Replicate	19	5916.94	311.42	1.24	2.15e-01 ns
Residuals	757	189599.87	250.46		

Significance codes: > 0.05 ' ns = not significant ', ≤ 0.05 ' * ', ≤ 0.01 ' ** ', ≤ 0.001 ' *** ', ≤ 0.0001 ' **** '

8.3 Timetable from 30.09.25

Phase	Task	Start Date	End Date	KW	Comment
Initiation	Create Task description	15.09.25	29.09.25	38-40	
	Kick-Off Meeting	19.09.25	19.09.25	38	
Concept	Create timetable	26.09.25	02.10.25	40	
	1. Checkpoint	02.10.25	02.10.25	40	
	Create risk map	02.10.25	05.10.25	40	
Implementation	Literature review	06.10.25	30.11.25	40-48	Ongoing task. Steadily learning.
1. Milestone	Define objective evaluation metrics	06.10.25	26.10.25	41-43	
	2. Checkpoint	16.10.25	16.10.25	42	
	Find 2-3 tools to evaluate	27.10.25	09.11.25	44-45	
	3. Checkpoint	30.10.25	30.10.25	44	
2. Milestone	Utility analysis (Nutzwertanalyse)	10.11.25	16.11.25	46	
	4. Checkpoint	13.11.25	13.11.25	46	
	Train AI with datasets	17.11.25	30.11.25	47-48	
	5. Checkpoint	27.11.25	27.11.25	48	
	Create listening test	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
Deployment					
3. Milestone	Present listening test to colleagues	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
4. Milestone	Perform subjective tests with sonova	08.12.25	21.12.25	50-51	
	6. Checkpoint	11.12.25	11.12.25	50	
	Deadline BAA	05.01.26	05.01.26		

	Milestone is in timeline
	Milestone is slightly behind
	Milestone unattainable

8.4 Timetable from 29.10.25

Phase	Task	Start Date	End Date	KW	Comment
Initiation	Create Task description	15.09.25	29.09.25	38-40	
	Kick-Off Meeting	19.09.25	19.09.25	38	
Concept	Create timetable	26.09.25	02.10.25	40	
	1. Checkpoint	02.10.25	02.10.25	40	
	Create risk map	02.10.25	05.10.25	40	
Implementation	Literature review	06.10.25	30.11.25	40-48	Ongoing task. Steadily learning.
1. Milestone	Define objective evaluation metrics	06.10.25	26.10.25	41-43	
	2. Checkpoint	16.10.25	16.10.25	42	
	Find 2-3 tools to evaluate	27.10.25	09.11.25	44-45	
	3. Checkpoint	30.10.25	30.10.25	44	
2. Milestone	Utility analysis (Nutzwertanalyse)	10.11.25	16.11.25	46	
	4. Checkpoint	13.11.25	13.11.25	46	
	Train AI with datasets	17.11.25	30.11.25	47-48	
	5. Checkpoint	27.11.25	27.11.25	48	
	Create listening test	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
Deployment					
3. Milestone	Present listening test to colleagues	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
4. Milestone	Perform subjective tests with sonova	08.12.25	21.12.25	50-51	
	6. Checkpoint	11.12.25	11.12.25	50	
	Deadline BAA	05.01.26	05.01.26		

	Milestone is in timeline
	Milestone is slightly behind
	Milestone unattainable

8.5 Timetable from 26.11.25

Phase	Task	Start Date	End Date	KW	Comment
Initiation	Create Task description	15.09.25	29.09.25	38-40	
	Kick-Off Meeting	19.09.25	19.09.25	38	
Concept	Create timetable	26.09.25	02.10.25	40	
	1. Checkpoint	02.10.25	02.10.25	40	
	Create risk map	02.10.25	05.10.25	40	
Implementation	Literature review	06.10.25	30.11.25	40-48	Ongoing task. Steadily learning.
1. Milestone	Define objective evaluation metrics	06.10.25	26.10.25	41-43	
	2. Checkpoint	16.10.25	16.10.25	42	
	Find 2-3 tools to evaluate	27.10.25	09.11.25	44-45	
	3. Checkpoint	30.10.25	30.10.25	44	
2. Milestone	Utility analysis (Nutzwertanalyse)	10.11.25	16.11.25	46	
	4. Checkpoint/Midterm Presentation	13.11.25	13.11.25	46	
	Train AI with datasets	17.11.25	30.11.25	47-48	
	5. Checkpoint	27.11.25	27.11.25	48	
	Create listening test	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
Deployment					
3. Milestone	Present listening test to colleagues	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
4. Milestone	Perform subjective tests with sonova	08.12.25	21.12.25	50-51	
	6. Checkpoint	11.12.25	11.12.25	50	
	Deadline BAA	05.01.26	05.01.26		

	Milestone is in timeline
	Milestone is slightly behind
	Milestone unattainable

8.6 Timetable from 12.12.25

Phase	Task	Start Date	End Date	KW	Comment
Initiation	Create Task description	15.09.25	29.09.25	38-40	
	Kick-Off Meeting	19.09.25	19.09.25	38	
Concept	Create timetable	26.09.25	02.10.25	40	
	1. Checkpoint	02.10.25	02.10.25	40	
	Create risk map	02.10.25	05.10.25	40	
Implementation	Literature review	06.10.25	30.11.25	40-48	Ongoing task. Steadily learning.
1. Milestone	Define objective evaluation metrics	06.10.25	26.10.25	41-43	
	2. Checkpoint	16.10.25	16.10.25	42	
	Find 2-3 tools to evaluate	27.10.25	09.11.25	44-45	
	3. Checkpoint	30.10.25	30.10.25	44	
2. Milestone	Utility analysis (Nutzwertanalyse)	10.11.25	16.11.25	46	
	4. Checkpoint/Midterm Presentation	13.11.25	13.11.25	46	
	Train AI with datasets	17.11.25	30.11.25	47-48	
	5. Checkpoint	27.11.25	27.11.25	48	
	Create listening test	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
Deployment					
3. Milestone	Present listening test to colleagues	01.12.25	07.12.25	49	
4. Milestone	Perform subjective tests with sonova	08.12.25	21.12.25	50-51	
	6. Checkpoint	12.12.2025	12.12.2025	50	
	Deadline BAA	05.01.26	05.01.26		

	Milestone is in timeline
	Milestone is slightly behind
	Milestone unattainable

8.7 Aufgabenstellung/Task description

Modul:	BAA
Titel:	Transforming normal speech into raised-vocal-effort speech
Ausgangslage und Problemstellung:	<p>In hearing research and the hearing device industry, psychoacoustic experiments are widely used to understand user behaviour and preferences. In order to simulate hearing conditions as realistic as possible, experiment participants are often presented with audio-visual material to increase realism. This enables companies to evaluate in laboratories the performance of their devices in conditions that are representative of the conditions experienced by future users in the real life.</p> <p>In order to design such perceptual experiments, specific audio and video footage needs to be produced prior to the beginning of recording sessions. The content of these videos strongly depends on the hypothesis to be tested in the experiments, which means that previously available material often cannot be reused. The production of the audio-visual sequences to be played during experiments is time-consuming and costly, depending also on the exact requirements. These requirements might include for example having many speakers with different voice characteristics, or a large corpus of spoken sentences.</p> <p>On the other hand, the quality of computer-generated media has increased dramatically in the last few years thanks to generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models. These include for example transformers, conformers, and diffusion models, which have seen an increase in popularity thanks to tools such as Midjourney, Stable diffusion, ChatGPT, and many others.</p>
Ziel der Arbeit und erwartete Resultate:	<p>This work will investigate the use of generative AI to produce synthetic audio material for psychoacoustic experiments, similarly to what is frequently seen on social media platforms in the form of so-called DeepFakes.</p> <p>The focus will be on transforming normal speech into raised-vocal-effort (Lombard) speech.</p> <p>This essentially means, that a person will be able to record an audio where they speak normally. Using a tool, that recording will be converted to Lombard speech. Humans naturally adjust for example their volume when it's very noisy in their surroundings. The goal is, to list existing transformation methods, to identify suitable objective evaluation metrics and then evaluate different methods for the conversion process. After finding the right tool, the next goal is to produce a listening test in collaboration with Sonova and to perform the subjective evaluation.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of literature (find papers, tools, methods, datasets etc.) • Define objective evaluation metrics • Select 2–3 methods/tools, re-implement them, and evaluate them. • Include a short listening test as part of the evaluation. • Tests with subjective evaluation metrics (depending on availability from Sonova)
Gewünschte Methoden, Vorgehen:	<p>Review of literature, Re-implementation and evaluation of the tools via objective evaluation metrics (for example volume), support Sonova's subjective evaluation.</p> <p>The student will present her work to the supervisor on bi-weekly meetings. One day before the meeting, the student will share a 1-page document describing in bullet points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What work was performed during the last reporting period. • What work is planned for the next period. • Project status, comparison with planning, reasons for deviations if applicable. • Top three risks incl. planned measures. <p>For the meeting, the student will prepare slides to present these information in more details.</p>
Kreativität, Methoden, Innovation:	<p>Tools for artificial media content generation are improving and multiplying very rapidly, and the use case to be investigated in this work is unique. Finding a way to achieve the desired goals therefore requires a fast, smart and creative problem solver. An effective solution would be truly innovative in the sector, drastically reducing the effort to set up audio-visual psychoacoustic experiments and potentially improving the quality of their outcomes.</p>
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9 Directories

9.1 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis Of Variance
BAA	Module "Bachelordiplomarbeit" at HSLU
BGMM	Bayesian Gaussian Mixture Model
dB	Decibels
DTW	Dynamic-Time-Warp
EMALG	Enhanced Mandarin Lombard Grid
F0	Fundamental Frequency
FFP2	Filtering Facepiece 2
HASPI	Hearing Aid Speech Perception Index
HASQI	Hearing Aid Speech Quality Index
Hertz	Hz
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MCD	Mel-Cepstral Distance
MGC	Mel-Generalised Cepstrum
MS	Miliseconds
NS	Not Significant
PML	Pulse model in the log domain
RMS	Root Mean Square
SCC	Spectral Cross-Correlation
Sound pressure level	SPL
SSC	Speaking Style Conversion
TTS	Text-To-Speech
VOC	Parametric vocoder
Words per minute	WPM

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9.4 List of AI-Tools

AI-supported tool	Last time used	Use case	Section in text	Comments
DeepL	21.11.25	Translation of text	Whole thesis	From German to English
Grammarly	03.01.26	Correction of grammatical and stylistic errors	Whole thesis	Premium Plan with Microsoft-Word-Integration
ChatGPT	19.10.25	Combining objective evaluation metrics into one file	Chapter 5.2	
ChatGPT	15.10.25	Help in converting and creating the pipeline	Chapter 5.3, Chapter 5.4,	
ChatGPT	01.11.25	Help in creating the pipeline	Chapter 5.5	

10 Bibliography

- Admin.ch, D. (n.d.-a). *Definition of the HERMES method*. Retrieved October 10, 2024, from <https://www.hermes.admin.ch/hermes5/en/project-management/understanding/overview-hermes/method-overview.html>
- Admin.ch, D. (n.d.-b). *Phases and milestones*. Retrieved October 11, 2024, from <https://www.hermes.admin.ch/hermes5/en/project-management/understanding/phases-and-milestones.html>
- Ana Ramirez, L., Shreyas, S., Lauri, J., Okko, R., & Paavo, A. (2017). *Speaking style conversion from normal to Lombard speech using a glottal vocoder and Bayesian GMMs* [Aalto University]. https://acris.aalto.fi/ws/portalfiles/portal/15741928/ramirez_interspeech0400.pdf
- Bajibabu, B., Lauri, J., & Paavo, A. (2019). *Lombard Speech Synthesis using Transfer Learning in a Tacotron Text-to-Speech System* [Aalto University]. https://www.isca-archive.org/interspeech_2019/bollepalli19_interspeech.pdf
- Bosker, H. R., & Cooke, M. (2020). *Enhanced amplitude modulations contribute to the Lombard intelligibility benefit: Evidence from the Nijmegen Corpus of Lombard Speech*. <https://hrbosker.github.io/publication/bosker-etal-2020-jasa>
- ElevenLabs. (n.d.). *ElevenLabs' Models*. Retrieved December 15, 2025, from <https://elevenlabs.io/docs/overview/models>
- Garnier, M., & Nathalie, H. (2013). *Speaking in noise: How does the Lombard effect improve acoustic contrasts between speech and ambient noise?* <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0885230813000557>
- Hang, L. (2024). *Machine Learning Methods*. Tsinghua University Press. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-981-99-3917-6>

Hill, P. R. (2018). *Audio and Speech Processing with MATLAB*. CRC Press.

<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.1201/9780429444067/audio-speech-processing-matlab-paul-hill>

Jacquelin, M., Garnier, M., Girin, L., Vincent, R., & Perrotin, O. (2025). *The French Lombard Dataset* [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533058>

James M., K., & Kathryn H., A. (2022). *An overview of the HASPI and HASQI metrics for predicting speech intelligibility and speech quality for normal hearing, hearing loss, and hearing aids*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378595522001769>

Kanetkar, R. (2023, April 12). *Hot AI startup ElevenLabs, founded by ex-Google and Palantir staff, is set to raise \$18 million at a \$100 million valuation. Check out the 14-slide pitch deck it used for its \$2 million pre-seed*. <https://www.businessinsider.com/elevenlabs-ai-voice-intelligence-startup-raises-2-million-2023-1>

Lee, J., Ali, H., Ziaei, A., Emily, A. T., & John H L, H. (2017). *The Lombard effect observed in speech produced by cochlear implant users in noisy environments: A naturalistic study*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5398925>

Li, Baifeng and Liu, Qingmu and Yang, Yuhong and Chen, Hongyang and Tu, Weiping and Lin, & Song. (2023). *EMALG : An Enhanced Mandarin Lombard Grid Corpus with Meaningful Sentences* (No. arXiv:2309.06858) [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2309.06858>

Moshona, C. C., Rudawski, F., Fiebig, A., & Sarradj, E. (2024). *The Berlin Dataset of Lombard and Masked Speech (BELMASK)* [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10730795>

Najwa, A., Steve, M., Ricard, M., Jon, B., & Guy J., B. (2018). *A corpus of audio-visual Lombard speech with frontal and profile views*, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 143 (No. EL523) [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5042758>

Newbold, P., Thorne, B., & Carlson, W. (2019). *Statistics for Business and Economics*. <https://elibrary.pearson.de/book/99.150005/9781292315201>

Qiong, H., Tobias, B., Petko, P., Tuomo, R., Erik, M., & Varun, L. (2021). *WHISPERED AND LOMBARD NEURAL SPEECH SYNTHESIS* [Apple].

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9383454>

R., K. (2025). *Mel-cepstral distance measure for objective speech quality assessment*.

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/407206>

Shreyas, S., Lauri, J., Okko, R., & Paavo, A. (2019). *Vocal Effort Based Speaking Style Conversion Using Vocoder Features and Parallel Learning* [Aalto University].

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8631106>

Sonova AG. (n.d.). *Homepage Sonova AG*. Retrieved June 10, 2025, from

<https://www.sonova.com/de>

Stefan, T., & Jasmin, S. (2025, April 14). *Mel-cepstral-distance 0.0.4*.

<https://pypi.org/project/mel-cepstral-distance>

The PyClarity Team. (2025, September 4). *Pyclarity 0.8.0*. <https://pypi.org/project/pyclarity/>

Yuxi, L., & Saransh, M. (2019). *Hands-On Deep Learning Architectures with Python*. Packt

Publishing. [https://app.knovel.com/kn/resources/kt01209O04/kpHODLAP12/pdf?b-](https://app.knovel.com/kn/resources/kt01209O04/kpHODLAP12/pdf?b-toc-cid=kpHODLAP12&b-toc-root-slug=hands-deep-learning-architectures&b-toc-title=Hands-On%20Deep%20Learning%20Architectures%20with%20Python&b-toc-url-slug=section-1-elements-deep&kpromoter=federation)

[toc-cid=kpHODLAP12&b-toc-root-slug=hands-deep-learning-architectures&b-toc-](https://app.knovel.com/kn/resources/kt01209O04/kpHODLAP12/pdf?b-toc-cid=kpHODLAP12&b-toc-root-slug=hands-deep-learning-architectures&b-toc-title=Hands-On%20Deep%20Learning%20Architectures%20with%20Python&b-toc-url-slug=section-1-elements-deep&kpromoter=federation)

[title=Hands-On%20Deep%20Learning%20Architectures%20with%20Python&b-toc-url-](https://app.knovel.com/kn/resources/kt01209O04/kpHODLAP12/pdf?b-toc-cid=kpHODLAP12&b-toc-root-slug=hands-deep-learning-architectures&b-toc-title=Hands-On%20Deep%20Learning%20Architectures%20with%20Python&b-toc-url-slug=section-1-elements-deep&kpromoter=federation)

[slug=section-1-elements-deep&kpromoter=federation](https://app.knovel.com/kn/resources/kt01209O04/kpHODLAP12/pdf?b-toc-cid=kpHODLAP12&b-toc-root-slug=hands-deep-learning-architectures&b-toc-title=Hands-On%20Deep%20Learning%20Architectures%20with%20Python&b-toc-url-slug=section-1-elements-deep&kpromoter=federation)